

THE UTILIZATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCES ON STUDENTS' ACADEMIC PERFORMANCE

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The Utilization of Artificial Intelligences on Students' Academic Performance

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Abstract. The rapid integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in education has transformed the ways students access information, complete academic tasks, and support their learning processes. This study examined the level of AI utilization and its relationship with the academic performance of Grade 11 students at Buenavista Integrated School in Zamboanga City during the School Year 2025–2026. Specifically, it assessed students' use of selected AI tools—ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva—and determined whether their utilization was associated with students' academic performance as measured by their General Weighted Average (GWA). A descriptive–correlational quantitative research design was employed. Data were collected from 113 Grade 11 students from the GAS, HUMSS, and TVL strands using a researcher-developed questionnaire based on a four-point Likert scale to measure AI utilization. Academic performance data were obtained from students' first-semester GWA records. Descriptive statistics, including mean and standard deviation, were used to determine the level of AI utilization, while Pearson correlation analysis was applied to examine the relationship between AI utilization and academic performance. Results revealed that students moderately utilized AI tools for academic purposes ($M = 2.81$, $SD = 0.62$). Among the platforms, Meta AI showed the highest level of utilization, followed by ChatGPT, while Canva recorded the lowest mean score. Students' academic performance was satisfactory ($M = 82.29$, $SD = 4.89$). However, the correlation analysis indicated a weak and statistically non-significant relationship between AI utilization and academic performance ($r = 0.131$, $p > 0.05$). The findings suggest that while AI tools are increasingly used by students to support academic tasks, their utilization does not directly translate into improved academic performance. AI platforms therefore function primarily as supplementary learning resources rather than primary determinants of academic achievement. The study highlights the importance of guided and responsible AI integration in educational settings to maximize its pedagogical benefits.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence in Education, AI Utilization, Academic Performance, ChatGPT, Meta AI, Canva

Introduction

In today's digital world, artificial intelligence (AI) plays an increasingly important role in the way people live, work, and make everyday decisions. Its growing presence has changed not only routine tasks but also how individuals interact with information, technology, and even with one another. As noted by Tuomi et al. (2018), AI has already reached levels that exceed certain human abilities. Among the most familiar AI platforms today are ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva. ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI, is an advanced language model that can assist with a wide range of tasks such as brainstorming ideas, planning experiments, and drafting proposals (Han, Qiu, & Lichtfouse, 2024). Meta AI, created by Meta (formerly Facebook), aims to

offer more than a simple chatbot. Its goal is to provide a multimodal and multilingual AI assistant capable of handling more complex and interactive tasks (Pazur, 2025). Canva, on the other hand, is a graphic design platform launched in 2012 by Australian entrepreneur Melanie Perkins, its drag-and-drop interface makes it easy to use for both beginners and professional designers (Gehred, 2020). In recent years, Canva has also integrated AI features to help users create designs more quickly and creatively.

Students' academic performance is a multifaceted concept influenced by various factors (Arifin, A., et al. 2024). The academic performance of students is a central concern in the field of education, with profound implications for their future success and societal well-being (Suleiman, I.B., et al., 2024). Academic performance is defined as grade point average, standardized test scores, and educational aspirations and attainment, reflecting students' grades and academic attitudes such as liking school and wanting to attend.

This study aims to determine the utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) on students' academic performance. The effective integration of artificial intelligence in education requires a thorough understanding of both the technology and the learning process (Vieriu, A. M., Petrea, G., (2025). Artificial Intelligence can significantly enhance students' academic performance and help them in various aspects of their learning. AI improves learning for students by providing them with possibilities for experiential or hands-on learning, particularly when paired with other technologies like virtual reality; 3-D, gaming, and simulation. (Rosak-Szyrocka, J. 2024).

Although research has explored AI and academic performance, most studies focus on non-educational settings or international contexts. For example, Mallilin (2024) reports positive effects of AI on students' motivation and study habits, but does not distinguish outcomes based on specific AI tools or academic subjects. Similarly, Hanshaw and Sullivan (2025) begin to explore the reasons behind students' non-utilization of AI course assistants; however, their study does not directly examine how these barriers impact academic performance. As such, there remains a gap in the literature regarding the practical use of AI in education settings—specifically, how students understand and utilize various AI platforms and how this usage correlates with measurable academic outcome. This study addresses that gap by examining student level of AI utilization and their usage patterns across different AI tools, such as ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva, in relation to their academic performance.

This study was conducted at Buenavista Integrated School in Zamboanga City, a school that offers Senior High School education. This school was served as the location where we will administer the survey questionnaire to the chosen population. AI platforms such as ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva are becoming somewhat familiar to students—whether they are using them to complete assignments, conduct research, or enhance creativity in their projects. As these tools become more accessible and widely used. It is important to determine how students engage with them, the extent of their understanding of these technologies, and whether their use had an impact on their academic performance.

Research Questions

This study aimed to assess the utilization of Artificial Intelligences (AI) and its relationship to the academic performance of Grade 11 Senior High School students at Buenavista Integrated School for the School Year 2025–2026.

Specifically, it sought to answer the following questions:

1. What is the level of Artificial intelligences utilization among senior high school students in terms of;
 - 1.1 ChatGPT
 - 1.2 Meta AI
 - 1.3 Canva
2. What is the level of students' academic performance?
3. Is there a significant relationship between the utilization of Artificial Intelligences and students' academic performance?

Scope and Delimitation of the Study

This study examined the use of artificial intelligences (AI) and its impact on the academic performance of Senior High School students at Buenavista Integrated School, Zamboanga City Division, during the school year 2025–2026. It focused on students' use of AI-powered tools such as Canva, ChatGPT, and Meta AI, and how these technologies supported their learning and academic improvement. The study specifically targeted Grade 11 students, who participated by responding to a structured questionnaire. By concentrating on this group, the research aimed to provide focused and relevant insights into how AI tools were integrated into students' learning experiences and whether their use contributed to improved academic performance.

Literature Review

Utilization of Artificial Intelligences

Artificial Intelligence (AI) utilization in education refers to the use of AI tools to support teaching, learning, and academic tasks. Studies show that Artificial Intelligence in Education (AIED) has the potential to improve learning experiences by providing faster access to information, personalized support, and efficient academic assistance (Estrellado & Miranda, 2023). In the Philippine setting, Villarino (2025) found that AI is increasingly being used in schools for lesson preparation, content creation, and learner support; however, most studies focus on urban institutions, leaving rural and non-urban schools underrepresented. To address this gap, Ignalig, De Los Santos, and Bauyot (2024) examined educators' knowledge and attitudes toward ethical AI integration and found generally positive perceptions, although concerns about data privacy and responsible use remain. Overall, these studies suggest that while AI utilization in education offers significant benefits, careful and ethical implementation is necessary to ensure its effective and equitable use.

ChatGPT

ChatGPT, developed by OpenAI, is one of the most widely used artificial intelligence tools in education due to its ability to generate human-like responses and provide academic support. Studies show that ChatGPT helps promote independent and self-directed learning by offering real-time feedback, personalized explanations, and adaptive learning support (Ali et al., 2024). It is commonly used as a virtual assistant for answering academic questions, supporting writing tasks, and assisting learners in online and self-paced learning environments (Education Sciences, 2024). However, the increasing use of ChatGPT has raised concerns related to ethical use, academic integrity, and over-reliance on AI tools, highlighting the need for responsible integration in educational settings (Albadarin et al., 2023; Rudolph et al., 2023). In the Philippine context, ChatGPT is gradually being adopted in higher education, particularly after the shift to digital learning during the pandemic, where it supports students in research, writing, and personalized learning (Dana et al., 2023). Despite its potential, challenges such as unequal internet access, limited institutional support, and varying levels of AI literacy affect its effective use, especially in rural areas (Song & Song, 2023). Recent studies emphasize that developing students' meta-AI literacy—understanding how AI works, evaluating its outputs, and using it ethically—is essential to ensure fair, responsible, and effective use of ChatGPT in education (Generale et al., 2025; Kasneci et al., 2023; Eldeen et al., 2023).

Meta AI

Meta AI is an artificial intelligence tool used in platforms like Facebook, Instagram, and WhatsApp, making AI more accessible for students (Meta, 2024). AI literacy involves not just using AI, but also understanding, evaluating, and applying it responsibly, including ethical considerations (Carolus et al., 2023; Ibrahim et al., 2025). In the Philippines, AI use in education is still growing, with studies showing gaps in students' awareness, skills, and ethical use of AI (Generale et al., 2024). Many Filipino students use Meta AI chatbots for learning, but there are concerns about overreliance and limited guidance from schools (Hernandez et al., 2025). Policies, digital literacy programs, and parental controls are recommended to ensure AI is used responsibly and effectively (Ortutay, 2025; Milmo, 2025). Strengthening students' meta-AI literacy is important to support ethical, balanced, and meaningful use of AI in learning.

Canva

Canva is a digital design platform that has transformed how students and teachers create visual and multimedia content, promoting creativity, digital literacy, and student engagement (Sugiami, Widiastuti, & Tahrun, 2024). Its user-friendly templates and collaborative features allow learners to produce infographics, presentations, and digital portfolios, making classroom activities more interactive and student-centered (Gurning et al., 2024; Yuniawati & Priyana, 2024). Studies in the Philippines show that Canva enhances students' digital design skills, engagement, and collaboration, although challenges such as internet connectivity and occasional overreliance on the platform can limit its use (Pedroso et al., 2023; Gabay & Amolo, 2025). Incorporating Canva into teaching also supports 21st-century skills, multimodal literacy, and critical thinking, making it a valuable tool for improving learning experiences and academic outcomes (Catubig et al., 2024). Overall, research indicates that Canva has strong potential to enhance both teaching effectiveness and students' academic performance when implemented with proper guidance and access.

Students' Academic Performance

Students' academic performance is influenced by a combination of psychological, behavioral, and institutional factors. Research shows that student engagement, motivation, and academic self-efficacy play a

major role in achieving better learning outcomes, as students who are confident and actively involved tend to persist and perform well (Meng & Zhang, 2023; Aj & Bouayad, 2024). Studies in the Philippines highlight that study habits, time management, family support, and learning environment significantly affect academic achievement (Garcia, 2025; Giray et al., 2025; Al Husaini & Shukor, 2022). Government programs, parental guidance, and supportive relationships with teachers and peers also contribute to improved performance by reducing barriers and increasing motivation (Gillespie, 2020; Le et al., 2025). Additionally, students' interest in learning and satisfaction with instruction positively influence academic success, emphasizing the importance of engaging teaching methods (Fathonah et al., 2025). Emerging research shows that the integration of Artificial Intelligence (AI) in education, when paired with active engagement and proper guidance, can enhance academic performance through personalized and learner-centered approaches (Villaver & Cabigas, 2025; Tamayo et al., 2025). Overall, these studies suggest that academic achievement is shaped by a combination of personal habits, environmental factors, support systems, and responsible use of technology.

Methodology

Research Design

This study employed a descriptive-correlational quantitative research design to examine the relationship between utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI) and students' academic performance. According to Creswell (2017), a descriptive-correlational design is effective for examining the relationship between variables as they naturally occur, without any manipulation, making it an appropriate choice for this study. The descriptive component was used to determine the level of Artificial Intelligences utilization such as ChatGPT, Meta AI, Canva and the level of students' academic performance. The correlational component examined whether a significant relationship exists between AI utilization and academic performance.

Sampling Design

The sampling method used in this study was non-probability sampling, specifically total enumeration. The respondents were selected from Buenavista Integrated School under the Zamboanga City Division. Total enumeration was employed to include all students who qualified within the target population, allowing for a complete representation without sampling. This method enabled the researcher to focus on students' utilization among artificial intelligences (AI) and their academic performance, which was central to the study. It also allowed for a more detailed analysis of how the utilization of AI tools, such as ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva related to students' academic performance. Since total population sampling involved all members of the population of interest, it provided deeper insights into the phenomenon you are interested in (Laerd Dissertation, 2012).

Research Locale

This study was conducted at Buenavista Integrated School in Zamboanga City during the School Year 2025–2026. Buenavista Integrated School was selected as the research locale due to its significant student population, which was sufficient to obtain appropriate respondents and makes it suitable for examining the level of utilization of AI-assisted tools such as ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva. The school had one (1) principal and offered education at the Elementary (Grades 1–6), Junior High School (Grades 7–10), and Senior High School (Grades 11–12) levels. The Senior High School department offered three strands: General Academic Strand (GAS), Humanities and Social Sciences (HUMSS), and Technical Vocational Livelihood (TVL).

Research Participants

This study presents the total population (113) of students-respondents in three selected strands. The largest number of participants (63) is in Grade 11 Tvl, while the smallest number (25) is in Grade 11 Humss and Gas. The sample size of 113 respondents is equal to the total population, as the study utilize total enumeration, wherein all qualify individuals from the population were included as respondents.

Research Instrument

This study included all Grade 11 senior high school students of Buenavista Integrated School. The total population of student-respondents was 113 across three strands under the Grade 11 curriculum: HUMSS, GAS, and TVL. The largest number of students (63) was from the TVL strand, while both HUMSS and GAS had 25 students each. Since complete enumeration was used, the total sample size was also 113 students, with all students from each strand included in the study.

Data Gathering Procedure

The researcher obtained approval from the Research Adviser, which was submitted to the Administrative Officer to request an Endorsement Letter from the Division Office, required to conduct research within the school district. With the Endorsement Letter, permission was sought from the principal of Buenavista Integrated School. After approval, all necessary documents—including the endorsement letter,

principal’s approval, consent forms, and the survey questionnaire—were submitted to the Junior High School Department coordinator. Student respondents were recruited through face-to-face visits, and only those willing to participate were included. The survey was administered during students’ free time, with clear instructions provided and questions addressed immediately to ensure understanding. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, highlighting voluntary participation and confidentiality, and the survey was conducted in person to provide guidance and assistance as needed.

Results and Discussions

Problem 1: What is the level of Artificial Intelligences utilization among Senior high school students in terms of ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva?

Table 1: The Level of Artificial Intelligences utilization among Senior high school students in terms of ChatGPT

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. I find ChatGPT difficult to use when I need simple, direct instructions.	2.78	.62	Agree	Moderately Utilized
2. I use ChatGPT to clarify lessons I do not fully understand.	3.07	.47	Agree	Moderately Utilized
3. ChatGPT does not contribute to improving my academic performance.	2.52	.61	Agree	Moderately Utilized
4. I use ChatGPT to generate ideas for essays or projects.	2.99	.51	Agree	Moderately Utilized
5. I sometimes receive incorrect information from ChatGPT.	2.94	.71	Agree	Moderately Utilized
6. ChatGPT saves me time in researching school-related topic.	3.01	.61	Agree	Moderately Utilized
7. Using ChatGPT reduces my confidence in performing tasks independently.	2.69	.67	Agree	Moderately Utilized
8. ChatGPT has a significant positive impact on my performance.	2.72	.64	Agree	Moderately Utilized
9. ChatGPT is unreliable for academic purposes.	2.75	.63	Agree	Moderately Utilized
10. I use ChatGPT to review and edit my assignments.	2.88	.69	Agree	Moderately Utilized
Over-all Mean	2.84	.62	Agree	Moderately Utilized

Table 1 shows the level of ChatGPT utilization among Senior High School students. The highest mean score of 3.07 (SD = 0.47) was recorded for the statement, “I use ChatGPT to clarify lessons I do not fully understand,” indicating that students primarily use ChatGPT to comprehend difficult lessons. This was followed by “ChatGPT saves me time in researching school-related topics” (M = 3.01, SD = 0.61), suggesting its usefulness in faster academic research. All statements had mean scores ranging from 2.52 to 3.07, verbally described as “Agree” and interpreted as “Moderately Utilized,” showing that students moderately use ChatGPT for lessons, idea generation, and assignment review, though concerns about accuracy remain. These findings align with Kasneci et al. (2023) and Tlili et al. (2023), who reported that AI tools enhance understanding and save time, improving learning efficiency. The lowest mean score of 2.52 (SD = 0.61) was recorded for “ChatGPT does not contribute to improving my academic performance,” suggesting that students are less certain about its direct effect on overall performance compared to specific academic uses. This indicates that ChatGPT has a moderately positive impact when used appropriately, as its interactive and relevant responses support understanding and engagement (Smith et al., 2024). Teachers are advised to guide students to use ChatGPT as a supplemental tool rather than a replacement for active learning, consistent with Luckin et al. (2016), who highlighted that AI tools can enhance learning outcomes by complementing traditional teaching methods.

Table 2: The Level of Artificial Intelligences utilization among Senior high school students in terms of Meta AI

Statements	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description	Interpretation
1. Meta AI often gives inaccurate information, making it difficult for me to trust.	2.80	.69	Agree	Moderately Utilized
2. I use Meta AI to search for academic-related information.	2.85	.63	Agree	Moderately Utilized
3. Meta AI provides incorrect answer.	2.52	.71	Agree	Moderately Utilized

4.	I rely too much in Meta AI for my essay.	2.36	.71	Agree	Moderately Utilized
5.	Meta AI helps me understand lesson better.	2.82	.55	Agree	Moderately Utilized
6.	I ask Meta AI to help me generate new ideas on my class project.	2.96	.58	Agree	Moderately Utilized
7.	Meta AI is confusing to use for school-related tasks	2.67	.56	Agree	Moderately Utilized
8.	Meta AI is helped me improved my academic performance	2.76	.54	Agree	Moderately Utilized
9.	Meta AI provides results that are not useful in my daily activities.	2.63	.63	Agree	Moderately Utilized
10.	Meta AI helps me summarize lengthy readings for academic performance	2.92	.55	Agree	Moderately Utilized
Over-all Mean		3.15	.62	Agree	Moderately Utilized

Table 2 shows the level of Meta AI utilization among Senior High School students. The highest mean score of 2.96 (SD = 0.58) was recorded for “I ask Meta AI to help me generate new ideas for my class projects,” indicating that students primarily use Meta AI for idea generation. This was followed by “Meta AI helps me summarize lengthy readings for academic purposes” (M = 2.92, SD = 0.55), showing that students also use it to manage academic content more efficiently. All indicators had mean scores ranging from 2.36 to 2.96, verbally described as “Agree” and interpreted as “Moderately Utilized.” These results suggest that students moderately use Meta AI for tasks such as idea generation, summarizing readings, and supporting schoolwork, while still expressing concerns about accuracy and reliability. The lowest mean score of 2.36 (SD = 0.71) was reported for “I rely too much on Meta AI for my essay,” indicating that students are cautious about over-reliance for producing their own work. While Meta AI provides timely and convenient information, students must critically assess outputs for accuracy and reliability (Johri et al., 2024). Balanced AI utilization is essential, where technology supports rather than replaces cognitive effort. Similarly, Holmes et al. (2023) emphasize that evaluating AI-generated content is a key skill in fostering digital literacy and responsible technology use. These findings highlight that careful and reflective use of Meta AI can enhance learning outcomes.

Table 3: The Level of Artificial Intelligences utilization among Senior high school students in terms of Canva

<i>Statements</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Verbal Description</i>	<i>Interpretation</i>	
1. I struggle to use Canva’s features because they are not user-friendly.	2.62	.63	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
2. Canva enhances my creativity in designing academic outputs	3.08	.68	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
3. Canva often becomes unresponsive or slow.	2.54	.62	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
4. Canva helps me improve the quality of my school project.	3.08	.70	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
5. Canva has not been helpful to me this school year.	2.33	.79	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
6. Canva limits my creativity because many designs look similar.	2.82	.57	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
7. I find Canva easy to use for my school-related work.	3.01	.55	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
8. Canva is time-consuming to use for simple school projects.	2.87	.59	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
9. Canva has help me improve in my academic performance.	3.01	.55	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
10. I use Canva to collaborate with classmates on group tasks.	3.01	.55	Agree	Moderately Utilized	
Over-all Mean		2.55	.62	Agree	Moderately Utilized

Table 3 shows that Senior High School students moderately utilize Canva for academic purposes. The highest mean score of 3.08 (SD = 0.68) was recorded for “Canva enhances my creativity in designing academic outputs,” indicating that students agree it supports creative work. This was followed by “Canva helps me improve the quality of my school projects” (M = 3.03, SD = 0.70), showing reliance on Canva to enhance output quality. Overall, mean scores ranged from 2.33 to 3.08, all interpreted as “Moderately Utilized,” suggesting students commonly use Canva for creating and improving projects, organizing information, and collaborating with classmates. These findings are consistent with Pedroso et al. (2025), who

reported that Canva’s features improve work quality, and Hutapea et al. (2024), who highlighted its role in promoting collaboration and engagement during project-based tasks. The lowest mean score of 2.33 (SD = 0.79) was reported for “Canva has not been helpful to me this school year,” reflecting a lower perceived usefulness. Students also indicated moderate agreement with items related to technical difficulties, time consumption, ease of use, and repetitive designs, showing challenges in using Canva effectively. Previous studies support these findings; Kurniawati and Fitriani (2021) noted limitations such as restricted free templates and technical issues, while Sama and Al Hashimi (2020) highlighted that overreliance on templates can limit creativity and originality. Overall, while students find Canva helpful, its limitations reduce its full potential in supporting academic tasks.

Table 4: Summary of the Levels of Artificial Intelligence Utilization

Indicators	Mean	Standard Deviation	Interpretation
ChatGPT	2.84	.62	Moderately Utilized
Meta AI	3.03	.62	Moderately Utilized
Canva	2.55	.62	Moderately Utilized
Over-All Mean	2.81	.62	Moderately Utilized

Table 4 presents the summary of AI utilization among Senior High School students across three tools: ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva. The overall mean score of 2.81 (SD = 0.62) indicates that AI tools are moderately utilized. Meta AI recorded the highest mean of 3.03, suggesting moderate use for tasks such as information searching, concept clarification, and schoolwork assistance. ChatGPT followed with a mean of 2.84, reflecting use for idea generation, writing support, and understanding complex lessons. Canva had the lowest mean score of 2.55, indicating less frequent use, although it still supports presentations and creative academic outputs. These findings indicate that students are aware of AI tools and integrate them into their academic activities to a moderate extent, though utilization is not maximized due to factors such as limited access, technical skills, or lack of guidance. Holmes et al. (2019) emphasized that AI enhances learning when students are properly guided, and Luckin et al. (2016) noted that AI serves as a supportive tool rather than a replacement for traditional teaching. Similarly, Zawacki-Richter et al. (2019) reported that AI integration in education is still developing. Overall, the moderate utilization reflects growing acceptance of AI in education and highlights the need for proper orientation, training, and policies to promote responsible and effective use for improved academic outcomes.

Problem 2: What is the level of students’ academic performance?

Table 5: Academic Performance of the Students for the 1st Semester, School Year 2025-2026

Indicator	Mean	Standard Deviation	Verbal Description
General Weighted Average Grade	86.50	4.89	Satisfactory

Table 5 shows the academic performance of the students for the 1st Semester, School Year. 2025–2026, based on their General Weighted Average (GWA). With a mean score of 82.29, described as “Satisfactory”, the results means that most students were able to meet the expected academic standards and performed reasonably well throughout the school year. These findings indicate that the students are generally able to meet the expected learning competencies, although they have not yet attained a high level of academic excellence. This means that while most learners demonstrate sufficient understanding of their subjects, there is still room for improvement in deeper and more advanced learning. According to the Department of Education (2015), a general average within this range reflects acceptable mastery of subject matter and adherence to the prescribed curricular standards. In a similar vein, previous studies suggest that a satisfactory level of academic performance implies that students have acquired the essential knowledge and skills needed for academic progression; however, additional instructional support and enrichment activities are often necessary to further develop higher-order thinking skills and improve overall academic achievement (OECD, 2019).

Problem 3: Is there a significant relationship between the utilization of Artificial Intelligence and students’ academic performance?

Table 6: The Significant relationship between the utilization of Artificial Intelligence and students' academic performance

Variable Mean		R-Value	P-Value	Interpretation
X	Y			
Utilization of Artificial Intelligence (AI)	Student's academic performance.	.131	.245	Not Significant

Table 6 shows a weak positive relationship between AI utilization and students' academic performance, with an R-value of 0.131. However, this relationship is not statistically significant ($p = 0.223 > 0.05$), indicating that AI use does not have a meaningful effect on academic performance. Consequently, the null hypothesis, which states that there is no significant relationship between AI utilization and academic performance, is accepted. The lack of a significant relationship suggests that AI tools alone do not strongly influence academic outcomes. Other factors, such as teaching strategies, learning environment, student motivation, and access to educational resources, may play a more important role (UNESCO, 2022). This finding aligns with Roquero, Rollon, and Magbutong (2025), who reported a weak, non-significant correlation between AI use and mathematics achievement, and Heng, Alias, and Nasri (2025), who found no significant effect of AI use on overall academic performance in junior high students in China. In contrast, Seblian and Calos (2025) observed a moderate positive effect in Social Studies, suggesting that the impact of AI may vary by subject and integration method.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to established ethical standards in educational research to protect participants' rights and welfare. Approval to conduct the research was obtained from the Department of Education Division Office and the Principal of Buenavista Integrated School. Informed consent was secured from all participants after explaining the study's purpose, procedures, and their right to participate voluntarily or withdraw at any time without consequence. Confidentiality and anonymity were strictly maintained, with participants identified using codes and no personal information disclosed in the analysis or report. Access to academic records was granted only with proper authorization and handled in accordance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (Republic Act No. 10173). All data were used solely for research purposes and stored securely. The study ensured participants were not exposed to physical, psychological, or emotional harm. Survey questions were non-intrusive, and data collection occurred during students' free time to avoid disruption or coercion. Principles of fairness, objectivity, and academic integrity were upheld throughout the research process.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it can be concluded that senior high school students moderately utilize AI tools, specifically ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva, to support their academic activities. AI platforms are predominantly used for clarifying lessons, generating ideas, summarizing readings, and improving the quality of academic outputs. Despite their usefulness, students remain cautious about AI reliability, accuracy, and over-dependence, which affects the extent of utilization. Moreover, the study concludes that the utilization of AI does not have a significant impact on students' overall academic performance. While AI tools contribute to learning efficiency and creativity, they do not directly enhance academic achievement. Factors such as teaching methodologies, motivation, learning environment, and additional support mechanisms likely play a more crucial role in determining students' performance. AI tools should therefore be seen as supportive learning aids rather than primary drivers of academic success.

Recommenations

Based on these findings, that educators integrate AI tools like ChatGPT, Meta AI, and Canva into teaching strategies as supplementary resources to enhance learning comprehension, creativity, and efficiency. Teachers should provide guidance on proper usage, encourage critical evaluation of AI-generated content, and promote balanced utilization to prevent over-dependence. Additionally, students should be encouraged to use AI tools responsibly, verifying outputs for accuracy and complementing AI support with active learning strategies. School administrators may also consider organizing workshops or training sessions to improve digital literacy and AI competence, ensuring that AI becomes an effective aid to learning rather than a substitute for critical thinking and personal effort.

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